

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia: An Introduction

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Intergovernmental Relations (IGR) is an important body of activities or interactions occurring between governmental units of all types and orders, and how these orders/spheres of government communicate and collaborate with each other.¹²⁸ Being one of the principles that distinguishes federal systems from the non-federal ones,¹²⁹ IGR is an institutional and pragmatic device for dealing with the intricate relations in a multilevel setting. Particularly, Agranoff states:

‘Local governments are inextricably linked vertically to states and to their general governments through ranges of national-state programs, legal and fiscal considerations and horizontally linked with associated local governments and NGOs through partnering, contracting or other forms of externalization.’¹³⁰

De Villiers¹³¹ also puts that modern-day governments require the mechanisms and institutions of IGRs so as to implement policies and programs, maximize the standard of service delivery and optimally utilize scarce resources.

Local government basically shoulder two responsibilities. On the one hand, they have to perform as autonomous local self-governing entity. On the other hand, the same local governments are often responsible for implementing policies as an agent of the subnational and federal governments. At the interface of these dual roles of the local governments is IGRs either in the form of supervision and cooperation. Apart from federalism that shapes the urban governance and politics through the constitutional, territorial and political framework, the process of urbanization is another force that influences the governance of urban spaces. To this end, IGR can be presented –both in principle and practice– as an institutional mechanism to overcome the politically divided but functionally interconnected multilevel arrangements and to moderate the often subordinate status of local governments.

In fact, developed and mature federations like Switzerland have put settled systems of local governmental institutions and use intergovernmental bodies and forums for addressing their

¹²⁸ Deil Wright, *Understanding Intergovernmental Relations* (3rd edn, Brooks/Cole 1988).

¹²⁹ Allen Trench, ‘Intergovernmental Relations: In Search of a Theory’ in Scott Greer (ed), *Territory, Democracy and Justice: Regionalism and Federalism in Western Democracies* (Palgrave Macmillan 2006).

¹³⁰ Robert Agranoff, ‘Local Governments in Federal Systems: Intergovernmental Relations in the Governance Era’ (22nd IPSA World Congress, Madrid, July 2012) 1.

¹³¹ Bertus de Villiers, ‘Codification of “Intergovernmental relations” by way of Legislation: The Experiences of South Africa and Potential Lessons for Young Multitiered Systems’ (2012) 72 *ZaöRV* 671.

local demands.¹³²In contrast, in the context of Ethiopia, the involvement of urban local governments (ULGs) in IGRs is more of a requirement than for rural local government (RLGs) because urbanization has already brought a formidable internal change to the federal system. The first internal challenge stems from the fact that urbanization often appropriates a large area of land beyond municipal boundary as economic and functional spaces. This in turn raises land use and local boundary disputes between the city and neighboring rural local governments. The other challenge is related to the demographic pressure due to rural to urban migration process of urbanization in Ethiopia. According to the official estimates about 50 per cent of urban population growth in Ethiopia is accounted for by rural-urban migration. Both the horizontal physical expansion and migration induced pace of urbanization have produced different problems including informal housing, land use and local boundary disputes. It is however clear that a single ULG cannot handle these problems. The ULG needs cooperation from neighboring local government and supra-local governments for addressing the mismatch between municipal boundary and urban functional area. It is this condition that brings the IGRs imperative.

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¹³² Bulliard Pascal, 'Local Government in Switzerland' in Nico Steytler (ed), *The Place and Role of Local Governments in Federal Systems* (Konrad Adenauer-Stiftung 2005); Wolf Linder, *Swiss Democracy. Possible Solutions to Conflict in Multicultural Societies* (3rd edn, Palgrave Macmillan 2010).

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